

Coronavirus: A Cruel Wakeup Call to Humanity?

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The novel coronavirus was heard of in some part of the universe was originally thought to be distant.¹ Caught unawares the virus from virtual turned into reality as it was near home. Evidently unprepared, as this was an unchartered practical health dilemma that was nowhere in hindsight. Grappling with the acute unavailability of health infrastructure and medical aid globally, treatment was bleak for the influx of persons suffering, with no ray of hope, even as of today.² Adding to this outbreak of illness is the predicament of patients to be left on their own to die of suffering and shame; for no fault of theirs. “Death was a community occurrence in the past.”³ Not anymore!

Patients dying of COVID-19, die alone and lonely. As death for many has been sudden and instant it has left families grappling with the reality of the sudden demise and broken hearted as they have been robbed of the opportunity to pay their last respects for their dead loved ones.⁴

The Alarming Situation

Is this a wakeup call for all humanity, considering the change that has engulfed the ethical perspective of the rational cognition? It may rightly be thought so. The following instances are heart-breaking:

- The plummeting environmental degradation due to the increase in the universal population has invaded the natural ecosystem. The anthropocentric behaviour towards the biosphere wherein humans have begun to consume it purposefully for their benefit and disregarding the cry of nature, indicates Vaclav Smil, a Czech-Canadian scientist and policy analyst. He adds that “most of these [genetic and viral] transformations can be traced to purposeful harvesting or destruction of the planet’s mass of living organisms and reduction”⁵
- Religion and caste discriminations leading to atrocities on the weak and vulnerable segment of society. Denouncing religions that might threaten those in power is a form of paternalistic political dominance. Countries like Syria, Korea, Somalia and many others are waging wars even as they realise that they are killing human lives leaving behind a large number of women, children and wounded without any livelihood. War sees a surging number of civilians that are affected.⁶ Waging wars for power, territorial gain, revenge and the age-old reason for economic gains is fiercely taking precedence all around us
- The economic disparity leads to the entrapment of the lower income groups that are deeply submerged in poverty. The rich thrive in their wealth, that is leading to clusters of the population that are the labour class, are almost used as slaves. The opportunities provided to the poor are negligible in number. The overconcentration of providing educational, professional and health facilities to the elite class is deeply harrowing the lives of those at the lowest strata of society. According to the ILO,⁷ forced labour has been of serious international worry since 1930.⁸
- Crimes have escalated in number in recent times. “In 2018, Tijuana, Mexico had the highest murder rate of any city in the world, with 138.26 murders per 100,000 population.”⁹ The number of criminals incarcerated is higher than ever before. Crimes are on the rise due to drug and alcohol usage, domestic violence, sexual harassment, one of the growing criminal trends are of persons suffering with anxiety, depression and job loss.

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- Human beings are losing intrinsic value of each other, as people have begun to feel that one can be replaced by another. This is visible with the increase in the number of divorces, children moving overseas for better professional gains, who most often don’t come back to their parents. Joint families turning into nuclear families, further more spouses living separately in different cities as their profession requires so. Communities are growing smaller.
- Health care is a far cry for those who cannot afford it. The poor receive little or no health facilities. Allocation of resources is the toughest choice that health care persons make. Today with the coronavirus cases rising, deciding who gets treated and who is left out is an ethical issue, with no right or wrong answer. “Health care can involve tragic choices, value conflicts, and a certain amount of technical knowledge”¹⁰

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Call to Wake Up

Although vigorously prevalent, the above instances challenge us to ask into our own behaviour and perceive the reasons of human misbehaviour. There is the lack of sensitivity towards everything around. John Kavanaugh’s remark holds very true today, “It is the ability to take ownership of our responses to the world. Our engagement in the world is not automatic.”¹¹

With the ubiquitous influence of information and technology there is a decline between religion and people. Some believe that religion only gains its importance as people age.¹²

The digital age¹³ has more people turning agnostic. The one question that is often reiterated, “is religion helpful anymore?” This question raises doubts in the mind as people have lost faith

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in their religion. Some of these people having lost faith in their religion have turned to other religions or follow a different way of life and call it spiritual enlightenment.

With the advancement of science and technology humans were under the impression that every problem could be overcome with science. “Recent scientific developments teach us that even the material world is beyond our complete comprehension. Science struggles and stumbles in comprehending the world.”¹⁴

The pandemic disease has brought all humanity to their knees. People stopped praying for themselves, but now with the death toll rising to a frightening number to all corners of the earth, people are praying for each other, those that are suffering with the disease, and the family members of the bereaved. With no relief visible as of now, the constraints lie with us, as we combat the disease with whatever resources are available. So, the COVID-19 is a challenge to wake up and recognise our own humanity. It urges us to see each other as brothers and sisters. It invites us to look into the animals and plants as our own partners! It summons us to look after nature as our own “common home,” and not to exploit it. It counsels us to look into our values system and rediscover the beauty of sharing, collaboration and service, as opposed to greed, profit and egoism.

Concluding Challenge

As I conclude this article the one question that can be asked, why did we reach this far into a problem that is beyond the control of all the world’s researchers, physicians and politicians?

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Did we get overconfident as the world was turning into a super nuclear power? We believed that we can endure all, as time would be on our side. This adversity has hit us like a tsunami against our theory, our problem is moving at a faster pace than we can deal with.

Thus, we can affirm that the outbreak of the disease is nature’s cruel answer to our misbehaviour.

As the virus has had the ability to nudge us out of our oblivion, and brought us into reality, our trust in religion will draw us back to our faith.

¹ Disease outbreak news. *Pneumonia of unknown cause – China*. World Health Organisation. <https://www.who.int/csr/don/05-january-2020-pneumonia-of-unknown-cause-china/en/> January 5, 2020. Accessed on March 30, 2020.

² Today’s date: March 30, 2020.

³ Scaria Kanniyakonil. *Wait for God’s Call Catholic Perspective on Euthanasia*. Oriental Institute of Religious Studies India, 2011. p.-106.

⁴ Sofia Bettiza. *Coronavirus: How Covid-19 is denying dignity to the dead in Italy*. “BBC World Service” <https://www.bbc.com/news/health-52031539>. Accessed on March 31, 2020.

⁵ Vaclav Smil. *Harvesting the Biosphere: What We Have Taken from Nature*, MIT Press, 2012. ProQuest Ebook Central, <http://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/britishcouncilonline-ebooks/detail.action?docID=3339556>. Created from british councilonline- ebooks on 2020-03-31 09:23:37. Preface p.-VII.

⁶ Cameron Moore. *5 War. “Crown and Sword: Executive Power and the Use of Force by the Australian Defence Force”* ANU Press, Acton ACT, Australia, 2017, pp. 205–252. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctt1zgwk12.10. Accessed 1 Apr. 2020.

⁷ International Labour Organisation is a part of the United Nations.

⁸ Rodger Doyle. *Modern Slavery*. “Scientific American” vol. 294, no. 1, 2006, pp. 30–30. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/26061289. Accessed April 1, 2020.

⁹ Published by Statista Research Department January 28, 2020. *Crime and punishment around the world - Statistics & Facts*.

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https://www.statista.com/topics/780/crime/#dossierSummary__chapter_1 Accessed April 1, 2020.

- ¹⁰ Ed. Lisa A Eckenwiler. Felicia G. Cohn. *The Ethics of Bioethics Mapping the Moral Landscape*. The John Hopkins University Press, Baltimore, 2007. p.87.
- ¹¹ John F. Kavanaugh, S.J. *Who Count as Persons? Human Identity and the Ethics of Killing*. Georgetown University Press/ Washington, D.C. 2001. p.60.
- ¹² Alasdair Crockett. David Voas. *Generations of Decline: Religious Change in 20th-Century Britain*. "Journal for the Scientific Study of Religion" vol. 45, no. 4, 2006, pp. 567–584. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/4621936. Accessed April 1, 2020.
- ¹³ IGI Global Publisher of Timely knowledge. <https://www.igi-global.com/dictionary/resource-sharing/7562>. Defines 'Digital Age' as: The time period beginning in the 1970s with the advent of the personal computers providing the technological capabilities to transfer information freely and quickly. This period is also called the information age. Accessed April 1, 2020.
- ¹⁴ Stephen Jayard Susainathan. "Enriching Science with the Dharma of Jesus: A Philosophy of Science Perspective. Dharma of Jesus". *Jnanadeepa Pune Journal of Religious Studies*. Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth, Pune. July 2015. p.- 146